

SUCCESSFUL TREATMENT OF TAKAYASU ARTERITIS IN THE PRACTICE OF INTEGRATIVE MEDICINE : A CASE REPORT.

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Abstract

A case of a 31-year-old Asiatic woman with active Takayasu arteritis that resolved following two courses of homeopathic remedies in KUF-series is reported. Treatment for active Takayasu arteritis typically requires high doses of corticosteroids and cytotoxic agents. There is no reported benefit from homeopathic remedies in KUF-series, which include nosod, organ preparations and homeopathic medicine. The administered therapy resulted in stabilization of the pathological processes, improvement of patient's condition and quality of life. No side effects of using the homeopathic remedies in KUF-series were observed.

Takayasu arteritis can be successfully treated with nosods, organ preparations and homeopathic medicine in KUF-series.

Key words: homeopathic medicine in KUF-series, electro-acupuncture diagnosis by Voll, medicament testing.

Introduction

Takayasu arteritis is classically defined as a chronic, progressive, inflammatory, occlusive disease of the aorta and its branches, resulting in ischemia of the corresponding organs. Although Takayasu arteritis has a worldwide distribution, it is observed more frequently in Asia and India than in Western Europe and North America (1). Corticosteroids are the mainstay of the therapy for active Takayasu arteritis. However, additional cytotoxic agents may be required to achieve remission. .

Case report.

In January 2001 a 31-year-old Asiatic woman, 54 kg, was admitted to the Medical Center of Alternative Medicine. She complained of weakness, fatigability, recurrent dizziness when she

turned her head, blackouts, attacks of headache, episodes of paroxysmal tachycardia >150 bpm and pain in both upper limbs on physical exertion, as well as progressive loss of weight.

In 1979, when the patient was 9-years-old, she was bitten by a dog, and immunised with anti-rabies vaccine. The one and a half months later she started feeling severe pain, firstly, in the left, later in the right hip joint and the lumbar part of the spine. Her temperature rose to 38.5°C, ESR 50 mm/hr. Three years later (1981) she was admitted to the Research Institute of Pediatrics' of the Academy of Medical Sciences (Moscow), where, based on an X-ray image, she was diagnosed as having ankylosing spondylitis. For the next four years (1981-1985) the patient had been treated by NSAIDs, which had a positive effect: pain, fever and joint constraint disappeared. In 1985 the patient's condition worsened with recurrence of headaches and the rise in BP to 170/120 mm Hg. Investigation revealed that the left kidney did not function; the ultrasound scan showed that the kidney size diminished (the left kidney was 8.8 cm x 3 cm; the right one was 11.5 cm x 6 cm). Since August 1985, the arterial hypertension had become malignant with an episodes of acute left ventricle failure, haemoptysis and oliguria. The patient was thoroughly examined and the diagnosis of ankylosing spondylitis was dismissed based on the normal functions of the spine, absence of HLA B27, age and gender.

In December 1985 the patient was admitted to the Research Institute for Surgery named after Vishnevsky (Moscow) where rheovasography of her upper and lower extremities, echo-Doppler scanning, angiography of some vessels were performed. The angiography showed stenosis of the upper renal part of the aorta, stenosis of the right renal artery, marked stenosis of the left renal artery, occlusion of the upper mesentery artery. She was diagnosed as having Takayasu arteritis (Type III) with predominant lesion of the left renal artery, renovascular hypertension and a surgical operation was performed in two stages: renal vessels angioplasty and prosthesis of the abdominal part of the aorta. Morphologic examination of the vessels also confirmed the Takayasu arteritis diagnosis(2).

In February 1992, the patient's condition worsened. She was at the time going through her first successful pregnancy. She complained of progressive weakness, HT, pedal oedema and an episodes of paroxysmal tachycardia relapsed with a rate of 200 bpm. BP on legs rose to 200/120 mm Hg. The patient was treated with high doses of oral prednisolone and immunosuppressive therapy with cyclophosphamide. In 2000 the Doppler examination of vessels and angiography had shown: noncomplete occlusion and stenosis of both common carotid arteries (80% of the right common carotid artery), occlusion of the left subclavian arteries(80%), stenosis of the right subclavian artery(75%), occlusion of the superior mesenteric artery, stenosis of the abdominal artery. She refused from surgical removal of the affected arteries.

In January 2001, the patient came to us with the complaints described above. She looked markedly malnourished. On physical examination the upper-extremity pulses were absent bilaterally. Carotid bruits were audible in the both subclavian areas. BP in the left hand could not be obtained, in the right one it was 80/60 mm Hg. BP in the right leg it was 200/120 mm Hg and in the left leg it was 190/110 mm Hg. Pulses in the lower extremities were normal. Cardiac examination was normal with no murmurs audible. The erythrocyte sedimentation rate was normal. No other abnormalities were noted.

The patient was examined by the electro-acupuncture diagnostics according to R.Voll (EAV) with the use of “medicament testing” technique which allows to diagnose the patients for determining an ethological, nosological diagnosis of different diseases and selects a single and daily doses of allopathic as well a homeopathic medicine. (3,4).

When examining our patients, the nosod of rabies virus was tested on the meridians of nervous degeneration and the artery-venous-lymphatic vessels meridian (Voll). At the same time, we tested organ preparations: Hypothalamus, Adenohypophysis, Adrenal glands, Thyroid and Parathyroid glands and homeopathic medicines: Fucus vesiculosus, Calcium iodatum, Pulsatilla, Mercurius solibius Hahnemanni, Silicea, Belladonna. Then, the tested homeopathic medicines in KUF- series were transferred on the homeopathic pilulaes by the “imprinting” method and were prescribed to our patient(5).

The patient had taken the homeopathic medicine for one month; after that she was examined again. The patient stopped complaining of headaches, dizziness, pain in both hands on exertion, weakness, fatigability, pain in both upper limbs on physical exertion. Paroxysms of tachycardia became less frequent. At the time of the examination by Voll, the nosod of rabies virus existing earlier was not found.

In May 2001 the patient was again examined using the EAV, and according to the examination results, the following medicines were tested and then transferred on the homeopathic pilulaes : the organ preparations of the : Brachial artery, Femoral artery, Spleen artery, Abdominal part of the aorta, Superior cervical ganglion of the sympathetic trunk, Middle cervical ganglion. Homeopathic remedies - Phytolaca, Arnica montana, Barium carbonicum, Aesculus, Carduus marianus, Lachesis - were also used. For the next seven months the patient had had a stable remission, however, in January 2002, she began again complaining of fatigability, weakness and a decrease in work capacity.

For the first time, the nosod of herpes simplex virus was registered on the meridian of nervous degeneration. The patient explained that from time to time she had herpetic lesions on her lips. The daily dose of antiviral drug, acyclovir, was selected. The patient was administered by acyclovir, which the patient used during a long time under the EAV diagnosis control. As a consequence, the PCR test did not reveal herpes simplex virus in the patient’s blood. (2005, 2006).

Since that time, we have not observed Takayasu arteritis deterioration in our patient.. She gained 10 kg in body weight (in March 2008 her weight was 64 kg).The Doppler-examination of vessels at different levels made in May 2008 have shown that the pathologic process tended to stabilize and hemo-dynamically significant changes in the vessels have not been registered since that time. The Doppler-examination have shown: stenosis of the right subclavian arteries(80%), occlusion of the left subclavian artery(85%),stenosis of both common carotid arteries (75%).Rheovasography of cerebral vessels showed the blood flow within normal limits.

Later on, until the present time, the patient has had a stable remission of her pathologic process. However, she is under a physician’s control.

Discussion

Cell-mediated autoimmunity appears to play an important role in the mechanism of vascular injury. In our patient, the onset of Takayasu arteritis combined with affection of several systems (the nervous, cardiovascular systems) was caused by the immunization with the anti-rabies vaccine, when she was a 9-year-old girl. Systemic vasculitis (The American College of Rheumatology includes Takayasu arteritis), is known to develop under the influence of different etiological factors, e.g. after vaccination (6). We think that the immunization of our patient with the anti-rabies vaccine triggered the autoaggression with disorder of the immunoregulation processes. Our case may be considered to be the secondary autoimmune diseases with known etiological factor(7).

We believe, that the rabies virus, being a trigger of the autoimmune process in our patient, started up an autoimmune pathologic response with development of the chronic processes. The organs of endocrine system and immune system are closely interrelated. Therefore, to rehabilitate our patient with disorders in the immune system the initial course of treatment included the organ preparations of different parts of endocrine system: hypothalamus, adenohypophysis, adrenal glands, thyroid and parathyroid glands. Application of the nosod of rabies virus and organ preparations of endocrine glands had contributed to the normalization of the endocrine glands' functioning and, at the same time, had assisted to reduction of the immune response in the body.

Nosodes and organ preparations are homeopathic remedies which have been extracted from sterilized pathogenic substances, secretions, destroyed germs and organ extracts from human and animal bodies. The preparations are produced following the normal homeopathic procedure. Many nosodes come from pathogenic products, vaccines, bacteria and viruses and they work according to the isopatic principle, i.e. a very diluted substance, which has been agitated, will cure the same diseases. Homeopathic remedies in KUF series are the medicine which consist of 10 ampoules of its in different dilutions from D3 to D100 or D1000. (products of companies "Wala-Heilmittel", "Staufen-Pharma", Germany).

The cases of using the KUF- series homeopathy drugs in the therapy of different diseases are described, but they propose to be used in single uses, both the nosods and the organ preparations.(8). As a rule, the single dilutions of a homeopathy medicine are prescribed in classic homeopathy and it requires the much time to achieve the results of the therapy(9).

After the prescribed treatment, the patient's condition improved significantly. To reinstate the functions of the nervous and cardiovascular systems, the organ preparations of different arterial vessels and ganglions of the vegetative nervous system were used on the next course of the therapy. As a consequence, after the therapy, we observed a long remission of the pathological processes.

Our previous research in therapy for patients with chronic hepatitis B virus infection, patients, who were treated with nosods, organ preparations and homeopathic medicine in KUF-series, revealed their anti-inflammatory and immuno-modulating activity(10). Earlier we suggested a hypothesis that integration of virus into cellular structures of patient can be followed by changes

in the structure of substantially bound intracellular water (11). The changes in intracellular water in pathologic conditions have been studied. Time of spin-lattice relaxation in oncological cell was found to change; the amount of water bound to DNA is also increased, thermodynamic characteristics of the system DNA + bound water are changed. The time of protons' relaxation is also changed in water solution of healthy tissues of patient with tumor processes (12).

The importance of water to living processes is explained not only by its ability to form hydrogen bonds with other water molecules, but especially, by its capacity to interact with various types of biological molecules. Because of its polar nature, water readily interacts with other polar- and charged molecules such as acids, salts, sugars and various regions of proteins and DNA. There are many publications devoted to the problem of "water memory". The 'memory of water' is a popular phrase that is mostly associated with homeopathy and Jacques Benveniste following his and others research works. Nowadays, many scientists associate the "water memory" and homeopathy effects with the structure of liquid water. Rustum Roy describes liquid water like its remarkably similar analogue SiO₂, which is not a homogeneous structure at the molecular level. It is a dynamic equilibrium among changing percentages of assemblages of different oligomers and polymer species. (13). At normal temperature, liquid water consists of dynamic clusters of 50 - 100 water molecules, in which the H—bonds are constantly being made and broken. Recent research on hydrogen bonds in water provides some support for this 'memory' theory. The Swiss chemist, Louis Rey, found that the structure of hydrogen bonds in homeopathic dilutions of salt solutions is very different from that in pure water. He reached the conclusion that the phenomenon results from the vigorous shaking of solutions that takes place during homeopathic "successions". Studies on molecular clustering in water solutions showed that while a solution is becoming more and more diluted, very stable and larger aggregates (clusters) develop in dilute solutions than in more concentrated solutions. These clusters are of several micrometers in diameter. This means that residual molecular clusters of original substance might just be present in homeopathic dilutions (14).

We believe, that prescribing the KUF- series homeopathic remedies to patient, we, as a matter of fact, introduce clusters of water with different kinds of structure and sizes. Thus, in the specific time of their function, the body's cells can independently chose the clusters of water with the structure, size and form which they need. The hypothesis was suggested that application of homeopathic medicine in KUF- series, promotes the restore of structure of substantially bound intracellular water, which changes in the presence of different diseases, including viral diseases. Restoration of the structure of substantially bound intracellular water, to our opinion, may promotes to normalization of biophysical and biochemical processes inside cells.

Conclusion

Takayasu disease can be successfully treated with homeopathic medicine in KUF-series which include nosods, organ preparations and homeopathic remedies. It is possible to speak about the significance of two virus in the genesis of Takayasu disease in our patient, namely, those of rabies and herpes simplex. The administered therapy resulted in the stabilization of the pathologic process, improvement of our patient's condition and her quality of life.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Consent

Written informed consent was obtained from the patient for publication of this case report. A copy of the written consent and any accompanying images are available for review by the Editor-in-Chief of this journal.

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